

POLYCYCLIC SYSTEMS. PART VIII. SYNTHESIS OF SEVEN-MEMBERED RING COMPOUNDS

BY D. NASIPURI, R. ROY AND U. RAKSHIT

Several α -3-phenylpropyl- β -oxo-esters have been cyclised by polyphosphoric acid. Some of the substituted benzocycloheptene derivatives, thus obtained, have been employed for the synthesis of tricyclic systems (e.g., X) having the skeletal structure of colchicine, the second seven-membered ring being built up by the Dieckmann ring-closure.

The cyclisation of appropriate aryl-substituted β -oxo-esters by means of concentrated sulphuric acid, first initiated by Bougault (*Compt. rend.*, 1914, 159, 745) has received numerous applications in the synthesis of hydroaromatic compounds (cf. Pechmann, *Ber.*, 1883, 16, 516; Auwers and Moller, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1925, 109, 124; Fieser and Hersberg, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 1851; Bachmann and Holmen, *ibid.*, 1951, 73, 3660; Bardhan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 1848; Bardhan and Nasipuri, *ibid.*, 1956, 350; Nasipuri, *ibid.*, 1958, 2618; Anner and Miescher, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1946, 29, 586; Buchta and Güllich, *Chem. Ber.*, 1959, 92, 1366). Extensive sulphonation and ester exchange (hydrolysis) are, however, some of the chief disadvantages of this method, specially in the case of higher aromatic systems. The use of sulphuric acid and phosphoric acid mixture (Crowley and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 2001; Horning *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 5830, 5826, 5828; Koo, *ibid.*, 1953, 75, 1889) and, more recently, the use of polyphosphoric acid (Koo, *ibid.*, 1953, 75, 1891) have eliminated these side reactions to a great extent and considerably increased the yield of the cyclisation. The last named reagent, besides avoiding the undesirable side-reactions, permits stronger reaction conditions and thus ensures better yields. During our synthetic investigations in seven-membered ring compounds (Guha and Nasipuri, *Science & Culture*, 1960, 25, 492,) we felt that the Bougault-type of cyclisation of appropriately substituted β -oxo-esters (e.g., I) could be conveniently employed for the synthesis of polycyclic systems containing one or two seven-membered rings. A few cases of seven-membered ring-closure of this type are already in record (Koo, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 720, 723; Koo and Hartwell, *ibid.*, 1953, 75, 1625). In view of the current interest in the synthesis of seven-membered ring compounds related to colchicine and analogues (Frank *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1948, 70, 2314; Gutsche, *ibid.*, 1951, 73, 786; Gutsche and Seligman, *ibid.*, 1953, 75, 2579; Gutsche and Fleming, *ibid.*, 1954, 76, 1771; Crabb and Schofield, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 4276, and references cited therein; Loewenthal and Rona, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 114; Schreiber *et al.*, *Angw. Chem.*, 1959, 637), we desire to report the results of our investigations.

As guide experiments of seven-membered ring-closure, we investigated the cyclisation of a number of substituted ethyl α -3-phenylpropyl- β -oxobutyric esters (I: R = R' = H or OMe) with polyphosphoric acid at the room temperature over a period of 1 to 5 hours. It was found that though ethyl α -3-phenylpropyl- β -oxobutyrate (I: R = R' = H) itself could not be cyclised to any appreciable extent by polyphosphoric acid, the methoxylated derivatives (I: R = OMe; R' = H and I: R = R' = OMe) underwent cyclisation smoothly and the resultant benzocycloheptene derivatives (II: R = OMe; R' = H), m.p. 137° and (II: R = R' = OMe), m.p. 178°, were isolated in about 70% yield. This result is in agreement with the observation of Koo (*loc. cit.*) that the cyclisation is facilitated to a certain extent by the presence of alkoxy groups. The phenylpropyl alcohols, required for these experiments, were prepared in excellent yields by reduction of the corresponding cinnamic esters according to the procedure of Bouveault and Blanc.

The conditions of the ring-closure being thus established, the cyclisation of more complicated systems was next tried. Ethyl α -3-*m*-methoxyphenylpropyl- β -oxopimelate (IV : R = OMe ; R' = R'' = H ; n = 3), obtained by alkylating ethyl β -oxopimelate (III : n = 3) (Guha, Rakshit and Nasipuri, this *Journal*, 1960, **37**, 267 ; Hunter and Hogg, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 1922) with 3-*m*-methoxyphenylpropyl bromide, on similar treatment with polyphosphoric acid and subsequent hydrolysis yielded the unsaturated acid (IX : R = OMe ; R' = R'' = H ; n = 3), m.p. 175-76°. The dimethyl ester of the latter on the Dieckmann cyclisation, followed by hydrolysis, furnished the tricyclic ketone (V : R = OMe ; R' = R'' = H, with ring-B six-membered). In another experiment, phenethyl bromide was condensed with ethyl β -oxosuberate (III : n = 4) (Archer and Pratt, *ibid.*, 1944, **66**, 1656) and the resultant β -oxo-ester (VI) cyclodehydrated with concentrated sulphuric

acid (Bardhan and Nasipuri, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 350) to yield 8-(2-carboxy-3:4-dihydro-1-naphthyl)-valeric acid (VII), m.p. 124-25° in an excellent yield. Heating the corresponding dimethyl ester with powdered sodium in xylene and subsequent hydrolysis afforded the ketone (VIII).

Finally, it was intended, by suitable application of the Bougault cyclisation and the Dieckmann ring-closure, to synthesise compounds with two seven-membered rings. For this purpose, and with a view to synthesising octahydrodemethoxydeoxydeacetamidocolchicine (X: R = R' = R'' = OMe) (Rapoport *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 3693), ethyl ester of 3:4:5-trimethoxycinnamic acid (Rapoport and Campion, *ibid.*, 1951, 73, 2239) was reduced by sodium and ethanol. But instead of the desired γ -3:4:5-trimethoxyphenylpropanol, γ -3:5-dimethoxyphenylpropanol was obtained in 60% yield, the 4-methoxyl group being completely eliminated during reduction. Replacement of the central methoxyl group in a trimethylpyrogallol system by hydrogen during similar reduction is, however, quite well known (cf. Asahina, *Ber.*, 1936, 69B, 1643; Christiansen *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 948). Though failed in our original purpose, this reaction, nevertheless, might serve as a good preparative method for γ -3:5-dimethoxyphenylpropanol, which is difficult to obtain otherwise.

The bromide of the above alcohol was condensed with ethyl β -oxosuberate in the usual manner and the resultant β -oxo-ester (IV: R' = H; R = R'' = OMe; n = 4) cyclodehydrated with polyphosphoric acid. The gummy dicarboxylic acid (IX: R = R'' = OMe; R' = H; n = 4), obtained by hydrolysing the cyclised product, was purified through the dimethyl ester and the latter cyclised by heating with powdered potassium in toluene for 10 hrs. The product on hydrolysis afforded a ketone (V: R = R'' = OMe; R' = H), m.p. 135° in about 20% yield. The latter on the Huang-Minlon reduction (Huang-Minlon, *ibid.*, 1946, 68, 2487) furnished the deoxy compound (X: R = R'' = OMe; R' = H), m.p. 55-56°. The epoxy derivative, prepared by perbenzoic acid oxidation, melted at 121-23°. The ultraviolet absorption spectra of the deoxy compound are very similar to those of octahydrodemethoxydeoxydeacetamidocolchicine (X: R = R' = R'' = OMe) (Rapoport *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). A synthesis of the latter from γ -3:4:5-trimethoxyphenylpropanol (Nasipuri, Rakshit and Guha, *Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1960, Part III, p. 147) through the above sequence of reaction will shortly be reported elsewhere.

Investigations are being carried out at present, for the synthesis of the dicarboxylic acid (XII) through the cyclisation of the keto-ester (XI). The latter has been prepared by alkylation of the β -oxo-ester (IV: R = R' = R'' = OMe; n = 2) with ethyl bromoacetate, followed by hydrolysis and esterification (cf. Nasipuri, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1956, 1389). The dicarboxylic acid (XII) will subsequently be used as a starting material for the synthesis of colchicine and analogues.

EXPERIMENTAL

γ -3-Methoxy- and 3:4-dimethoxyphenylpropanols required in these experiments were prepared from the corresponding cinnamic acids. The latter were obtained in good yields from methoxylated benzaldehydes according to the procedure of Livshits *et al.* (*J. Gen. Chem. U.S.S.R.*, 1947, 17, 1671). In a typical preparation, 3:4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde (25 g.), malonic acid (32 g.), pyridine (50 c.c.) and piperidine (1 c.c.) were heated at 80° for 1 hr. and then for 2 hrs. at 100° and for 0.5 hr. at gentle reflux. The mixture was poured into excess of 12% HCl, filtered, washed, and dried to afford 3:4-dimethoxycinnamic acid (26 g.), m.p. 178-80°. Horning *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) record m.p. 180°. *m*-Methoxycinnamic acid, prepared in the same way, melted at 115°. The ethyl esters were obtained in the usual way by refluxing ethanol with sulphuric acid as catalyst. The esters were reduced by sodium and ethanol according to the following procedure,

A solution of ethyl 3:4-dimethoxycinnamate (26 g., m.p. 55-56°) in super-dry ethanol (160 c.c.) was added all at once to finely divided sodium (30 g.), preheated to a temperature of 80°. The temperature of the oil-bath was then raised to 135° and the molten sodium was pulverised by shaking the flask vigorously. When all the sodium had gone into solution (2 hrs.), the heating at 135° was continued for 2 hrs. more with the occasional addition of ethanol (3 × 20 c.c.). The cooled mixture was next decomposed with water (200 c.c.) and most of the alcohol removed by steam distillation. γ -3:4-Dimethoxyphenylpropanol was worked up in the usual way and distilled to furnish a colorless oil (13 g., 58%), b.p. 160-65°/2 mm. The alcohol formed 3:5-dinitrobenzoate readily which crystallised from ethanol in yellow needles, m.p. 110°. (Found: C, 55.2; H, 4.8; N, 7.3. $C_{18}H_{18}O_8N_2$ requires C, 55.4; H, 4.6; N, 7.2%).

The corresponding phenylpropyl bromide was prepared by treating the preceding alcohol (10 g.) with PBr_3 (7.5 g.) in CCl_4 (15 c.c.) at 60° for 30 mins. γ -3:4-Dimethoxyphenylpropyl bromide distilled at 145°/2mm. (Found: Br, 30.4. $C_{11}H_{15}O_2Br$ requires Br, 30.8%).

Ethyl α -3-Phenylpropyl- β -oxobutyrate (I: R=R'=H).—To a cold mixture of ethyl acetate (13 g.) and ethanolic sodium ethoxide (from sodium 2.3 g. and ethanol 50 c.c.) was added γ -phenylpropyl bromide (20 g.) and the whole was heated under reflux at 90° for 8 hrs. After removal of most of the ethanol, the residue was treated with cold 2N- H_2SO_4 and the organic matter taken up in ether. The ethereal extract was washed with water, dried and evaporated. The residue was distilled to furnish the β -oxo-ester (I: R=R'=H), b.p. 160-65°/2 mm. (Found: C, 72.5; H, 8.3. $C_{15}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 72.6; H, 8.0%).

Ethyl α -3-m-Methoxyphenylpropyl- β -oxobutyrate (I: R=CMe; R'=H), b.p. 175-77°/0.8 mm (Found: C, 68.8; H, 8.2. $C_{18}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 69.1; H, 7.9%) and *ethyl α -3-(3:4-dimethoxyphenyl)propyl- β -oxobutyrate* (I: R=R'=OMe), b.p. 190-95°/0.3 mm (Found: C, 66.0; H, 7.9. $C_{17}H_{24}O_6$ requires C, 66.2; H, 7.7%) were prepared in the identical way.

5'-Methoxy- and 4':5'-Dimethoxy-1:2-benzocyclohept-1:3-diene-3-methyl-4-carboxylic Acids (II: R=OMe; R'=H and II: R=R'=OMe).—(a). *Ethyl α -3-m-methoxyphenylpropyl- β -oxobutyrate* (I: R=OMe; R'=H) (2 g.) was kept in with polyphosphoric acid, prepared from phosphorus pentoxide (12 g.) and 89% phosphoric acid (10 c.c.) at room temperature for 1 hr. The red mixture was decomposed with ice-water and extracted thoroughly with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution, and then with water, dried, and the solvent evaporated to afford a neutral product (1.1 g.). This was hydrolysed with ethanolic KOH and the acid (II: R=OMe; R'=H) (1 g.), thus obtained, was crystallised from methanol to furnish needles, m.p. 137°. (Found: C, 72.3; H, 7.1; equiv., 232. $C_{14}H_{10}O_6$ requires C, 72.4; H, 6.9%; equiv., 232). The sodium bicarbonate extract on acidification yielded a further crop of the crystalline acid (0.3 g.), m.p. 130-32°.

Ethyl α -3-(3:4-dimethoxyphenyl)propyl- β -oxobutyrate (I: R=R'=OMe) on similar treatment afforded 4:5'-dimethoxy-1:2-benzocyclohept-1:3-diene-3-methyl-4-carboxylic acid (II: R=R'=OMe), m.p. 178°, yield 70%. (Found: C, 68.5; H, 6.9; equiv., 261. $C_{18}H_{18}O_6$ requires C, 68.7; H, 6.8%; equiv., 262). The yield could not be appreciably increased on prolonging the period of treatment with polyphosphoric acid to 5 hrs. or even more.

(b). Attempts to cyclise the β -oxo-ester (I: R=R'=OMe) with concentrated sulphuric acid (5 vol.) at 6° for 2-3 hrs. did not succeed.

Ethyl α -3-m-Methoxyphenylpropyl- β -oxopimelate (IV: R=OMe; R'=R''=H; n=3).—*m*-Methoxyphenylpropyl bromide (23 g.) was condensed with ethyl 4:6-dioxoheptane-1:5-dicarboxylate (27.2 g.) (Bardhan and Nasipuri, *loc. cit.*) in presence of ethanolic sodium ethoxide (from

sodium 2.3 g. and ethanol 40 c.c.) by heating the mixture at 90° for 10 hrs. It was then diluted with water, acidified and repeatedly extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and evaporated. The β -oxo-ester was finally obtained as a colorless oil (22 g.), b.p. 210-20°/0.6 mm. (Found: C, 66.8; H, 7.4. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_6$ requires C, 66.6; H, 7.9%.)

5'-Methoxy-1:2-benzocyclohept-1:3-diene-4-carboxyl-3- γ -butyric Acid (IX: R=OMe; R'=R''=H; n=3).—The preceding β -oxo-ester (9 g.) was treated with polyphosphoric acid (120 g.) for 5 hrs. at room temperature. The product was worked up as before and hydrolysed by boiling with 5% methanolic KOH solution to yield the crude *dicarboxylic acid* (5 g.) as a semisolid mass. The acid on several crystallisations from aqueous methanol was finally obtained in colorless needles (1 g.), m.p. 174-76°. (Found: C, 66.8; H, 6.6; equiv., 154. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_6$ requires C, 67.1; H, 6.5%; equiv., 152).

The *dimethyl ester* was prepared in the usual way by refluxing the acid with methanolic sulphuric acid, and had b.p. 210-12°/0.5 mm.

1':2':3':4'-Tetrahydro-7'-methoxy-1'-oxo-1:2:3:4-dibenzocyclohept-1:3-diene (V: R=OMe; R'=R''=H; ring-B six-membered).—The foregoing ester (1.6 g.) was added to a suspension of 'molecularised' sodium (0.12 g.) in dry thiophen-free benzene (5 c.c.) containing 2 drops of methanol, and the mixture refluxed for 4 hrs. The resulting β -oxo-ester was worked up in the usual way and hydrolysed with refluxing glacial acetic acid (20 c.c.), HCl (conc., 10 c.c.) and water (2 c.c.) for 30 mins. The *ketone* (0.5 g.) was purified through chromatography over alumina and afforded a red *dinitrophenylhydrazone* (from chloroform and methanol), m.p. 250-52°. (Found: C, 62.30; H, 5.2; N, 13.2. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_6\text{N}_4$ requires C, 62.6; H, 5.2; N, 13.3%.)

Ethyl α -Phenethyl- β -oxosuberate (VI).—Phenethyl bromide (22 g.) was condensed with ethyl β -oxosuberate (30 g.) (III: n=4) in presence of sodium ethoxide, prepared from sodium (3 g.) and absolute ethanol (50 c.c.), in the same way as described before. The condensation product, worked up in the usual way, on distillation furnished the β -oxo-ester (VI) as colorless oil (16.5 g.), b.p. 200-10°/0.4 mm. (Found: C, 68.7; H, 8.1. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_6$ requires C, 68.9; H, 8.0%.)

2-Carboxy-3:4-dihydro-1-naphthyl- δ -valeric Acid (VII).—The above β -oxo-ester (10 g.) was slowly added to well-stirred H_2SO_4 (conc., 65 c.c.), cooled in a freezing mixture. After allowing the mixture to stand for 3 hrs. at -5° to -10°, it was poured on crushed ice when a semisolid mass separated, which was extracted with ether. The residue after evaporation of the ether was hydrolysed with boiling ethanolic KOH (KOH 7 g., water 7 c.c. and ethanol 100 c.c.) for 3 hrs., affording the crude *dicarboxylic acid* (VII) (5.6 g.). On repeated crystallisation from benzene-petroleum ether (40-60°) it was obtained in thick prisms, m.p. 124-25°. (Found: C, 69.8; H, 6.4; equiv., 137. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 70.1; H, 6.6%; equiv., 137).

The acid (5.5 g.) was heated with a mixture of methanol (50 c.c.) and H_2SO_4 (conc., 3 c.c.) for 6 hrs., and the product on distillation furnished the *dimethyl ester* (5 g.), b.p. 180-90°/0.8 mm. (Found: C, 71.2; H, 7.4. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 71.5; H, 7.3%.)

1':2'-Dihydro-3':4'-naphtho-2:3-cyclohept-2-en-1-one (VIII).—The foregoing ester (3 g.) was refluxed with a mixture of pulverised sodium (1 g.), dry xylene (30 c.c.) and methanol (2 drops.) for 4 hrs. in nitrogen atmosphere. The resulting sodio-salt was then decomposed with water (100 c.c.), acidified with HCl and extracted with benzene. The residue after evaporation of the benzene was hydrolysed with boiling 0.5 N ethanolic KOH solution (100 c.c.) for 3 hrs. After removal of most of the ethanol, the organic matter was taken up in ether, the ethereal layer thoroughly washed with sodium carbonate solution, then with water, dried, and the solvent evaporated. The residue was distilled in high *vacuo* to furnish the *ketone* (VIII) as an oil (0.8 g.), b.p. 145-50°/0.2 mm. It

formed a *dinitrophenylhydrazone* which crystallised from ethyl acetate in dark red needles, m.p. 194°. (Found : C, 64.0 ; H, 4.9 ; N, 14.2. $C_{21}H_{20}O_4N_4$ requires, C, 64.3 ; H, 5.1 ; N, 14.3%).

γ -3 : 5-Dimethoxyphenylpropanol.—3 : 4 : 5-Trimethoxybenzaldehyde, prepared according to Cook *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 322), was converted into 3 : 4 : 5-trimethoxycinnamic acid in the same way as described before. The ethyl ester (20 g.) of the cinnamic acid was dissolved in super-dry ethanol (130 c.c.) and was added to sodium (25 g.), preheated to 80° in a flask fitted with an efficient condenser. The mixture was then heated rapidly to 135° in an oil-bath and the molten sodium was finely dispersed by shaking the flask vigorously several times. Heating was continued at 135-40° for 5 hrs. more with a further addition of ethanol (2×30 c.c.) towards the end, to ensure complete dissolution of sodium. The cooled mixture was then decomposed with water (100 c.c.) and the ethanol removed by steam distillation. The product on being worked up in the usual way afforded γ -3 : 5-dimethoxyphenylpropanol (9 g., 60%), b.p. 165°/0.2 mm. (Found : C, 67.4 ; H, 8.4. $C_{11}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 67.3 ; H, 8.2%). It formed 3 : 5-dinitrobenzoate, m.p. 141° (ethanol). (Found : C, 55.2 ; H, 4.8 ; N, 7.4 ; OMe, 15.7. $C_{16}H_{16}O_8N_2$ requires C, 55.4 ; H, 4.6 ; N, 7.2 ; OMe, 15.8%).

γ -3 : 5-Dimethoxyphenylpropyl Bromide.—A solution of the above alcohol (8 g.) in dry CCl_4 (10 c.c.) was treated with PBr_3 (1.8 c.c.) at 60° for 30 mins. The mixture was then poured over ice and the product worked up in the usual way to yield the bromide (8 g.), b.p. 140-45°/0.2 mm. (Found : C, 50.7 ; H, 6.0. $C_{11}H_{16}O_2Br$ requires C, 50.9 ; H, 5.8%).

3' : 5'-Dimethoxy-1 : 2-benzocyclohept-1 : 3-diene-4-carboxyl-3- δ -valeric Acid (IX : R=R''=OMe ; R'=H ; n=4).—Ethyl β -oxosuberate (10 g.) was added to a stirred solution of potassium (1.4 g.) in dry butanol (28 c.c.) in nitrogen atmosphere. γ -3 : 5-Dimethoxyphenylpropyl bromide (9.0 g.) was then rapidly added and the mixture heated under reflux for 12 hrs. Most of the alcohol was removed in the water-pump, the rest decomposed with acidulated water and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with water, dried, and the solvent evaporated. Fractions boiling up to 150°/0.2 mm were removed by distillation and the residue, which mainly consisted of the β -oxo-ester (IV : R=R''=OMe ; R'=H ; n=4), was used directly for cyclodehydration.

The above β -oxo-ester (3 g.) was kept in with polyphosphoric acid, prepared from 85% phosphoric acid (15 c.c.) and phosphorus pentoxide (20 g.), at room temperature for 5 hrs. The deep red solution was decomposed with ice and worked up as usual. The product on hydrolysis afforded the dicarboxylic acid (IX : R=R''=OMe ; R'=H ; n=4) (1.9 g.) as gum which could not be induced to crystallise. It was directly esterified with methanolic sulphuric acid, and the dimethyl ester obtained as viscous oil, b.p. 220-25°/0.2 mm. A good middle fraction was analysed. (Found : C, 67.6 ; H, 7.9. $C_{21}H_{28}O_6$ requires C, 67.0 ; H, 7.4%).

5 : 6 : 7 : 8 : 9 : 10 : 11 : 12-Octahydro-1 : 3-dimethoxy-8-oxobenzo [a] heptalene (V : R=R''=OMe ; R'=H).—The preceding ester (3 g.) in dry toluene (40 c.c.) was added during 1 hr. to a boiling suspension of potassium (1 g.) in toluene (15 c.c.) with vigorous stirring in nitrogen atmosphere. The reflux was continued for 8 hrs. more, the mixture cooled and decomposed with water. The organic matter was extracted with benzene, washed with water and the solvent evaporated in the water-pump. The residue (3 g.) was kept overnight with a solution of methanol (70 c.c.), potassium hydroxide (4 g.), and water (8 c.c.). Next day it was refluxed for one hour, acidified with HCl (22 c.c.) and heated for further 8 hrs. Methanol was then removed from the water-bath, organic layer extracted with benzene, washed with water, dried, and the solvent evaporated. The residual viscous oil (1 g.) was taken up in benzene and absorbed in an alumina column, and eluted with a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether (40-60°). The ketone (V ; R=R''=OMe ; R'=H) was

finally obtained in fine needles from methanol (400 mg.), m.p. 135°. (Found: C, 75.4; H, 7.8. $C_{18}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 75.5; H, 7.6%). The *dinitrophenylhydrazone* was crystallised from ethyl acetate-methanol in silky red needles, m.p. 239-40°. (Found: C, 61.4; H, 5.8; N, 12.1. $C_{24}H_{26}O_6N_4$ requires C, 61.8; H, 5.6; N, 12.0%).

5 : 6 : 7 : 8 : 9 : 10 : 11 : 12-Octahydro-1 : 3-dimethoxybenzo [a]heptalene (X : R=R''=OMe ; R'=H).—A mixture of the foregoing ketone (200 mg.), KOH (180 mg.), diethyleneglycol (3 c.c.), and 80% hydrazine hydrate (0.2 c.c.) was heated under reflux for 1½ hrs. Water was then distilled off until the temperature rose to 195°, when refluxing was continued for 4 hrs. longer. The cooled solution was diluted with water, acidified with HCl, and extracted with benzene (3×20 c.c.). The residue after evaporation of benzene was shaken for 2 hours at room temperature with 3*N*-NaOH (35 c.c.) and dimethyl sulphate (5 c.c.). The solution was then extracted with ether, washed with water, dried, and the solvent removed. The residue was passed through an alumina column in petroleum ether solution and the *deoxy compound* (X : R=R''=OMe ; R'=H) was finally purified by sublimation and crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) in colorless needles, m.p. 55-56°; λ_{max}^{OH} 256 and 283 m μ (log ϵ 4.00 and 3.80 respectively). (Found: C, 79.3; H, 8.9; OMe, 23.0. $C_{18}H_{24}O_2$ requires C, 79.4; H, 8.8; OMe, 22.8%).

Epoxidation of (X : R=R''=OMe ; R'=H).—The above *deoxy compound* (40 mg.) and 0.04*M* perbenzoic acid solution (16 c.c.) in chloroform were left for 4 hrs. at 0°, and then decomposed by the addition of *N*- K_2CO_3 solution (10 c.c.). The chloroform layer was separated, washed with water, dried, and the solvent evaporated. The residual solid was chromatographed (alumina) and crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) in needles, m.p. 121-23°. (Found: C, 74.8; H, 8.5. $C_{18}H_{24}O_3$ requires C, 75.0; H, 8.3%).

Methyl 4-Carbomethoxymethyl-3-oxo-7-(3 : 4 : 5-trimethoxyphenyl)heptane-1-carboxylate (XI : R=R'=R''=OMe).— γ -3 : 4 : 5-Trimethoxyphenylpropanol, prepared according to the method of Rapoport and Campion (*loc. cit.*), was converted into its *bromide*, b.p. 160-62°/2 mm, by the action of PBr_3 (*vide supra*). The *bromide* (29 g.) was condensed with ethyl β -oxoadipate (22 g.) in presence of potassium butylate' (from potassium 4 g. and butanol' 80 c.c.) by heating in the water-bath for 10 hrs. in nitrogen atmosphere. After removal of some of the alcohol in the water-pump, the residue was decomposed with acidulated water, extracted with ether, dried, and the solvent evaporated. The residue was distilled up to 150°/0.2 mm to remove low-boiling impurities as far as possible. The rest was treated with a solution of sodium (2.3 g.) in ethanol (50 c.c.), cooled, and ethyl bromoacetate (17 g.) was added. Next day, the mixture was refluxed on the water-bath for 6 hrs. and the product worked up in the usual way. The crude material (40 g.) was directly hydrolysed by refluxing with 2% aqueous NaOH solution (1 litre) for 10 hrs. The neutral matter was extracted with ether, the alkaline solution acidified, and the organic matter was taken up in ether. The ethereal solution was dried (Na_2SO_4), solvent evaporated, and the residue (23 g.) was esterified by heating with 3% methanolic HCl (300 c.c.). The product was worked up in the usual way and on distillation afforded the *ester* (XI : R=R'=R''=OMe) as viscous oil (15 g.), b.p. 220-30°/0.2 mm. A middle fraction was analysed. (Found: C, 61.7; H, 7.5. $C_{21}H_{30}O_8$ requires C, 61.5; H, 7.3%).

The cyclisation of the ester by means of polyphosphoric acid is under investigation.